

Grassland spiders of the Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the Free State (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides the first species list of spiders presently known and protected in the Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the Free State, South Africa. A total of 138 species from 104 genera and 36 families are presently known from the area. The most species-rich families are the Araneidae (21 spp.), Thomisidae (17 spp.) and Salticidae (14 spp.). A large number of the species have been photographed, including their webs. The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution is provided. Approximately 5.9 % of the total South African spider fauna is represented on the Estate.

Key words: checklist, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), webs

INTRODUCTION

Grasslands are ancient and date back to well before the break-up of the earth's landmass into continents and oceans. In the Afrotropical Region, true grasslands currently survive only in South Africa, and represent about 16.5% of the total land area. Grasslands are primarily found in the summer rainfall areas, from sea level to altitudes above 3000 m, and cover large parts of the Gauteng, Mpumalanga, Free State, Eastern Cape and North West provinces. The climate typically consists of warm, wet summers followed by cold, dry winters with heavy frosts. Frost, fire and grazing are some of the factors that prevent the spread of shrubs and trees. It is a unique ecosystem with a rich and often highly specialized fauna. The vegetation is dominated by grass species, with many forbs also present. Grasslands burn regularly, often every year, and the plants and animals are often adapted to survive fires (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida surveys are underway in grassland areas, with the main aim of documenting the diversity of the biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). The first checklist on the spiders of the Grassland Biome was published by Haddad *et al.* (2013), listing 58 families and 792 described species. A book on the Grassland species followed soon after (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014). There are many unique grass-dwelling spiders, with special adaptations in body form, colour, and web and retreat construction, such as retreats or egg sacs constructed in inflorescences, or as a framework for web construction. Many species have special adaptations in shape and colour that make them cryptic on grass. Many have become nocturnal to escape the high daytime temperatures in the summer and to utilize the large quantity of insects available at night. By preying on insects and even other arachnids, spiders are an important component in grassland food webs.

South Africa's spider species are not evenly distributed across the country and the highest diversity is recorded in the provinces of Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal (Foord *et al.* 2020). Many of the spider surveys of the Free State focused on the ground- (Lotz *et al.* 1991; Haddad *et al.* 2015; Haddad & Butler 2018; Neethling & Haddad 2019), termitaria- (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2002, 2006), foliage- (Haddad 2005; Fourie *et al.* 2013; Neethling & Haddad 2013), tussock- (Luwes & Haddad 2020; Haddad *et al.* 2021) and leaf litter-dwelling (Butler & Haddad 2011; Haddad *et al.* 2019) spider assemblages, all conducted in the central Free State.

The work we report on here was not conceived as a scientific study as such, but are the result of many observations and a photographic survey undertaken regularly over a 14-year period in a grassland fragment at Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the eastern Free State Province, South Africa (Fig. 1). No quantitative methods were used and the main focus was hand searching and observations on the grass inhabitants (Fig. 2).

METHODS

Study area: The survey was carried out in grassland at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) that is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands, some 14 km from Clocolan (Fig. 1). The MCE (28°48'S, 27°39'E) covers 164 ha and it is a registered conservancy (Amohela-ho-Spitskop), sanctuary and nature reserve. The estate is on average 1700 m above sea level, with an annual rainfall of 720 mm.

A 230-million-year-old koppie "Spitskop" is an integral part of the estate and is home to a rich natural heritage of Flora and Fauna (Figs 3 & 4). The second author (Allen Jones) and Jenny Lotter have been the owners of MCE since 2002.

FIGURE 1: Map of South Africa, showing the location of the Mpetsane Conservation Estate.

FIGURE 3: The 230-million-year-old koppie "Spitskop" at the Mpetsane Estate.

FIGURE 2: Survey at Mpetsane Conservancy Estate in 2007.

FIGURE 4: The grassland area at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate.

The grasslands have been re-wilded, wild flowers and plants have returned, with an abundance of insects and spiders. In 2005, the owners contacted the members of SANSa and initiated a survey to determine the arachnid diversity of the MCE, resulting in several reports in previous SANSa Newsletters.

Study method: The majority of observations were made by the second author (AJ). While staying on the reserve he was regularly walked in the field to photograph spiders and make observations. In March 2007, members of the Pretoria SANSa survey team undertook a collecting trip to MCE to collect arachnids (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2007). They were joined by Charles Haddad of the University of the Free State and Leon Lotz of the National Museum, Bloemfontein (Jones 2007).

Photography: As part of SANSa a Virtual Museum was developed where photographs could be submitted by the public as an additional method to plot the distribution of spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2012). More than 2000 photographs of the arachnids of MCE were taken over the years. This include a large series of web images (see Figs 5 & 6).

Specimens: Sampled arachnids were identified by the first (ASD) and third authors (CH). Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria. Material is also housed in the Arachnida Unit at the National Museum in Bloemfontein.

Endemicity value: The endemicity value was provided for each species (Appendix 1) based on its currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognized: 6 = MCE, known only from type locality (Mpetsane Conservation Estate); 5 = FSE, known only from the Free State Province but wider than the type locality; 4 = SAE known from two adjoining provinces (South African Endemic); 3 = South Africa, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining (SAE); 2 = STHE, known from southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic); 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider (C).

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider project, the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or where only very old material is available, or species that could not be identified were listed as DDT (data deficient for taxonomic reasons) or DD when there is a lack of distribution data. Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Family diversity: A total of 138 species from 103 genera and 36 families have been recorded from MCE to date, with the Araneidae (21 spp.), Thomisidae (17 spp.) and Salticidae (14 sp.) the most species-rich families (Table 1; Appendix 1). The dominant grass-dwelling families apparently vary geographically and according to grassland type. In the drier grasslands of the central Free State, the numerically dominant grass-dwelling families include Thomisidae, Philodromidae, Salticidae and Araneidae, although the abundance of each may vary between different grassland types (Haddad 2005; Fourie *et al.* 2013).

A large number of web-dwellers are listed, including several ground web-dwellers such as *Benoitia ocellata* of the Agelenidae (Figs 5a,f), *Chiasmopes namaquensis* (Roewer, 1955), *Euprosthops australis* Simon, 1898 and *Euprosthopsis pulchella* (Pocock, 1902) of the Pisauridae, and *Hippasa australis* Lawrence, 1927 (Lycosidae). Numerous plant web-dwellers are listed, such as the Araneidae (Fig. 5c, d, g, j), Dictynidae (Fig. 5e) and Eresidae (*Stegodyphus dumicola* Pocock, 1898).

The Araneidae (21 spp.) and Tetragnathidae (3 spp.) species are all orb-web dwellers, except *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) that make a reduced orb-web. Their large webs are visible early in the morning while still covered with dew (Figs 5b, g, j). Several of the araneid species were also recorded from the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.* 2013), but there were several species such as the three *Argiope* spp., *Argiope aurocineta* Pocock, 1898, *Argiope australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) (Jones 2012), *Argiope lobata* (Pallas, 1772), *Cyrtophora citricola* (Forsskål, 1775), and the two golden orb-web spiders, *Trichonephila fenestrata* Thorell, 1859 and *T. senegalensis annulata* (Thorell, 1859) Figs 5c, d, g), that were not previously recorded from surveys.

At MCE the populations of *Argiope australis*, *A. lobata*, *Cyrtophora citricola* (Fig. 5d) and *Trichonephila fenestrata* (Fig. 5c) sometimes built up to very high numbers during the year (Jones 2012a, b).

Several new species and new records have been reported from MCE. Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones (2008) reported on the first record of *Cyrtarachne ixoides* (Simon, 1870) (Araneidae) from South Africa. More recently, a small ground-dwelling spider was described, *Eleleis haddadi* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020, with MCE as the type locality. From *Eucalyptus* leaf litter another new species *Capobula montana* Haddad, Jin, Platnick & Booyesen, 2021 was described, but it is widespread in the Eastern Cape, Free State and Lesotho.

Species conservation and endemism: Of the 138 species sampled, only *Eleleis haddadi* is a MCE endemic. Two trapdoor spiders are Free State endemics, *Ancylotrypa dreyeri* (Hewitt, 1915) and *Stasimopus minor* Hewitt, 1915, as is the daddy long-legs spider *Quamtana lotzi* Huber, 2003 (Pholcidae). These four Free State endemic species are of particular concern, especially *Eleleis haddadi*, which is only known from one specimen from MCE.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Mpetsane Conservation Estate, with total number of families, genera (G) and species (S).

FAMILY	G	S	FAMILY	G	S
Agelenidae	1	1	Pholcidae	2	3
Araneidae	14	21	Phyxelididae	1	1
Caponiidae	1	1	Pisauridae	4	4
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	Salticidae	11	14
Clubionidae	1	3	Scytodidae	1	1
Corinnidae	4	5	Segestriidae	1	2
Cyrtachenidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	1
Dictynidae	1	1	Sicariidae	1	2
Eresidae	2	4	Sparassidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	6	6	Stasimopidae	1	1
Hahniidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	2	3
Hersiliidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	1	1	Theridiidae	6	9
Lycosidae	10	12	Thomisidae	12	17
Mimetidae	1	1	Trachelidae	4	5
Oxyopidae	2	4	Trochanteridae	1	1
Palpimanidae	1	1	Uloboridae	1	1
Philodromidae	3	5	Zodariidae	2	2

Five species could not be determined and were not evaluated, while four species were Data Deficient due to their unresolved taxonomy (Appendix 1). The majority of species (130) have a wide distribution and are considered to be of Least Concern.

CONCLUSION

This inventory adds some species to the Free State species list and provides some information on their behavior, especially for the web builders.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI), Threatened Species Programme for funding the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) phase 2. The authors also thank the staff of the Arachnology Unit of the Biosystematics Programme, ARC – Plant Health and Protection, for their assistance with processing and databasing the material collected. A special word of thanks to Jenny Lotter for her support.

FIGURE 5: Web images from Mpetsane Conservancy Estate. (A-B) Sheet and funnel-webs of the ground dwelling spiders including species of Agelenidae, Lycosidae and Pisauridae; (C) Dense orb-webs of the Araneidae species; (D) Adapted orb-webs of the Araneidae; (E) Retreat-webs of Dictynidae; (F) Funnel-web of Agelenidae; (G) Orb-webs Araneidae and Tetragnathidae; (H-I) Sheet-webs of Pisauridae and Lycosidae; (J) Orb-webs (Photos: A. Jones).

FIGURE 6: Common spiders of Mpetsane Conservation Estate. (A) *Gephyrota glauca* (Jézéquel, 1966) (Philodromidae); (B) *Rothus aethiopicus* (Pavesi, 1883) (Pisauridae); (C) *Oxyopes bothai* Lessert, 1915 (Oxyopidae); (D) *Camaricus nigrotesselatus* Simon, 1895 (Thomisidae); (E) *Tibellus minor* Lessert, 1919 (Philodromidae); (F) *Runcinia erythrina* Jézéquel, 1964 (Thomisidae); (G) *Euprosthops australis* Simon, 1898 (Pisauridae); (H) *Clubiona* sp. (Clubionidae); (I) *Baryphas ahenus* Simon, 1902 (Salticidae); (J) *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) (Araneidae); (K) *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon, 1875 (Thomisidae); (L) *Archaeodictyna conducta* (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876) (Dictynidae) (Photos: A. Jones).

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APPENDIX 1: Spiders of the Mpetsane Conservation Estate, listing their endemcity (END), conservation status (CS) and global distribution (DIST).

SPECIES	END	CS	DIST
1. Family Agelenidae			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
2. Family Araneidae			
<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
<i>Argiope aurocineta</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyrtarachne ixoides</i> (Simon, 1870)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Larinioides</i> sp. 1		NE	
<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona penicillipes</i> (Karsch, 1879)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
3. Family Caponiidae			
<i>Caponia hastifera</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
4. Family Cheiracanthiidae			
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
5. Family Clubionidae			
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Clubiona</i> sp. 3		NE	
6. Family Corinnidae			
<i>Cambalida dippenarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE
<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE
<i>Copuetta lacustris</i> (Strand, 1916)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE
7. Family Cyrtachenidae			
<i>Ancylotrypa dreyeri</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	5	DDT	SAE
8. Family Dictynidae			
<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
9. Family Eresidae			
<i>Dresserus kannemeyeri</i> Tucker, 1920	4	LC	SAE
<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
10. Family Gnaphosidae			
<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Eleleis haddadi</i> Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020	6	DDT	MCE

APPENDIX 2: - continued.

<i>Theuma maculata</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Xerophaeus appendiculatus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
11. Family Hahniidae			
<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
12. Family Linyphiidae			
<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	0	LC	C
13. Family Lycosidae			
<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE
<i>Amblyothele albocincta</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE
<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
<i>Trabea rubriceps</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
14. Family Mimetidae			
<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
15. Family Oxyopidae			
<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
16. Family Palpimanidae			
<i>Palpimanus</i> sp. 1		NE	
17. Family Philodromidae			
<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
18. Family Pholcidae			
<i>Quamtana lotzi</i> Huber, 2003	5	DD	FSE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
19. Family Phyxelididae			
<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
20. Family Pisauridae			
<i>Chiasmopes namaquensis</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Euprosthénops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Euprosthénopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
21. Family Salticidae			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE

APPENDIX 2: - continued.

<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
<i>Heliophanus prozysniskii</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
<i>Psenec dependens</i> (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Rhene lingularis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE
22. Family Scytodidae			
<i>Scytodes drakensbergensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	4	LC	SAE
23. Family Segestriidae			
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ariadna karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
24. Family Selenopidae			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
25. Family Sicariidae			
<i>Loxosceles parramae</i> Newlands, 1981	4	LC	SAE
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
26. Family Sparassidae			
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
27. Family Stasimopidae			
<i>Stasimopus minor</i> Hewitt, 1915	5	DDT	FSE
28. Family Tetragnathidae			
<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha demissa</i> L. Koch, 1872	0	LC	C
29. Family Theraphosidae			
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
30. Family Theridiidae			
<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	3	LC	SAE
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 2		NE	
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3		NE	
<i>Tidarren scenicum</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE
29. Family Thomisidae			
<i>Camaricus nigrotesselatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Firmicus bipunctatus</i> Caporiacco, 1941	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses gibbus</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1984	3	LC	SAE
<i>Oxytate concolor</i> (Caporiacco, 1947)	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE

APPENDIX 2: - continued.

<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisops sulcatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus urbensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
30. Family Trachelidae			
<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Capobula montana</i> Haddad, Jin, Platnick & Booyesen, 2021	2	LC	STHE
<i>Poachelas striatus</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	3	LC	SAE
<i>Thysanina absolve</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006	5	LC	FSE
<i>Thysanina transversa</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006	3	LC	SAE
31. Family Trochanteriidae			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1886)	1	LC	AE
32. Family Uloboridae			
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
33. Family Zodariidae			
<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE

Endemicity (END): (6) known only from the type locality, Mpetsane Conservation Estate; (5) endemic to the Free State Province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; FSE, Free State endemic.